

Solid Phase Reaction Between Basic Slag and Urea Nitrate

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Basic slag reacts with urea nitrate on grinding the powders of the two solids together. 1 : 3 ratio of basic slag to urea nitrate makes the phosphatic content of the slag nearly 98% water soluble and therefore it can be utilized to produce a mixed fertilizer. Amongst the various Indian basic slags the mixed fertilizer can be conveniently prepared only with the slags of Tatanagar, Burnpur and Durgapur as they contain fairly good amount of P_2O_5 in comparison to the slags of Bhilai, Bhadrabati and Rourkela.

THE ever increasing demand of super phosphate and other phosphatic fertilizers for more food production poses a great problem to countries having no natural resources of sulphur, as in the manufacturing process of these fertilizers huge amount of sulphuric acid is consumed. Many attempts have therefore been made to replace sulphuric acid by nitric acid. The recent finding of Viswanathan⁵ clearly indicates the feasibility of manufacturing nitrophosphates without the use of sulphuric acid. He observed that on grinding powdered rock phosphate with urea nitrate in a particular ratio the phosphatic content becomes completely water soluble. Disposal of basic slag (Thomas phosphate) is a problem in steel cities throughout the world. The analysis shows that it contains many essential ingredients for plant growth. Its use as a fertilizer is therefore of particular interest in this context. Investigations of Nydegger⁴ for the production of water soluble phosphatic fertilizer using rock phosphate and urea nitrate prompted us to study the possibility of rock phosphate replacement by basic slag. As urea nitrate itself is a nitrogenous fertilizer, the mixed product will be an excellent nitrophosphatic fertilizer containing water soluble P_2O_5 and other nutrients essential for better crop yield.

So far no attempt has been made to prepare a mixed fertilizer out of basic slag. In the present work a fixed quantity of each basic slag from different steel industries of India viz., Burnpur, Durgapur, Tatanagar, Rourkela, Bhilai and Bhadrabati was mixed and ground with different amounts of urea nitrate for making the slag phosphate water soluble so as to assess the utility of slags in nitrophosphate production.

Experimental

Basic slags from Burnpur, Durgapur, Tatanagar, Rourkela, Madhya Pradesh (Bhilai) and Karnatak (Bhadrabati) were powdered and sieved through a 100 mesh sieve. The powder passing through the

sieve was analysed¹ and used in the subsequent experiments.

Urea nitrate was prepared from urea (BDH) and nitric acid according to the procedure of Kutty and Murthy². It was purified by recrystallization from water.

As the basic slags of Rourkela, Bhilai and Bhadrabati do not contain much P_2O_5 , they were not used for further experiments. 1 g of each basic slag from the remaining places was mixed with different amounts of urea nitrate and ground in an agate mortar for 2 hr under dry conditions. The amount of P_2O_5 soluble when 1 g. of the mixture was leached with 250 ml. of conductivity water at 20° was taken as water soluble phosphate. The amount of P_2O_5 soluble in 100 ml. of 2% citric acid in the residue after leaching with water was taken as the citrate soluble phosphate. P_2O_5 was estimated volumetrically after precipitating with ammonium molybdate solution⁶.

The results are tabulated below :—

TABLE I—ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT INDIAN BASIC SLAGS

Ingre- dients	B.B.S. %	D.B.S. %	T.B.S. %	R.B.S. %	M.B.S. %	K.B.S. %
SiO ₂	15.95	27.16	14.60	33.12	20.51	25.02
FeO	19.30	5.54	28.00	0.58	9.32	10.21
MnO	4.68	5.00	3.20	2.52	9.14	10.47
CaO	41.72	36.05	32.73	33.33	43.49	39.39
P ₂ O ₅	3.58	3.21	7.84	0.26	1.49	0.88
Al ₂ O ₃	7.39	16.01	6.44	23.12	5.63	1.62
MgO	6.38	6.28	6.23	6.23	9.45	11.40
Available P ₂ O ₅	1.92	1.67	4.02	0.14	0.78	0.43

TABLE 2—WATER AND CITRATE SOLUBLE P₂O₅ IN UREA NITRATE BASIC SLAG MIXTURES

Basic Slag	Basic slag to Urea Nitrate Wt. ratio	Total P ₂ O ₅ %	Water soluble P ₂ O ₅ %	Citrate soluble P ₂ O ₅ %	Fraction of water soluble P ₂ O ₅ %	Fraction of citrate soluble P ₂ O ₅ %
B.B.S.		2.38	0.1861	0.9460	7.82	39.75
D.B.S.	1 : 0.50	2.14	0.1498	0.8722	7.00	40.76
T.B.S.		5.22	0.4102	2.0770	7.86	39.79
B.B.S.		2.04	0.5940	0.9249	29.12	45.34
D.B.S.	1 : 0.75	1.83	0.5149	0.8483	28.14	46.36
T.B.S.		4.48	1.3063	2.0330	29.16	45.38
B.B.S.		1.79	0.8115	0.4027	45.34	22.50
D.B.S.	1 : 1.00	1.60	0.0797	0.3763	44.36	23.52
T.B.S.		3.92	1.7778	0.8835	45.37	22.54
B.B.S.		1.59	0.9743	0.2973	61.28	18.70
D.B.S.	1 : 1.25	1.42	0.8420	0.2880	59.30	19.72
T.B.S.		3.48	2.1339	0.6518	61.32	18.73
B.B.S.		1.43	1.0102	0.2019	70.65	14.12
D.B.S.	1 : 1.50	1.28	0.8788	0.2065	68.66	16.14
T.B.S.		3.13	2.2122	0.4432	70.68	14.16
B.B.S.		1.30	1.0439	0.0627	80.30	4.83
D.B.S.	1 : 1.75	1.16	0.9085	0.0580	78.32	5.00
T.B.S.		2.85	2.2896	0.1382	80.34	4.85
B.B.S.		1.19	1.0802	0.0230	90.78	1.94
D.B.S.	1 : 2.00	1.07	0.9608	0.0283	89.80	2.65
T.B.S.		2.61	2.3698	0.0456	90.80	1.75
B.B.S.		1.02	0.9772	0.0122	95.81	1.20
D.B.S.	1 : 2.50	0.91	0.8628	0.0159	94.82	1.75
T.B.S.		2.24	2.1463	0.0264	95.82	1.18
B.B.S.		0.89	0.8794	0.0064	98.81	0.73
D.B.S.	1 : 3.00	0.80	0.7825	0.0084	97.82	1.05
T.B.S.		1.96	1.9368	0.0145	98.82	0.74

B.B.S. = Burnpur Basic Slag
 D.B.S. = Durgapur Basic Slag
 T.B.S. = Tatanagar Basic Slag
 R.B.S. = Rourkela Basic Slag
 M.B.S. = Madhya Pradesh (Bhilai) Basic Slag
 K.B.S. = Karnataka (Bhadrabati) Basic Slag.

Discussion

The analysis (Table 1) shows that although all the Indian basic slags contain some necessary ingredients for healthy plant growth, only slags of Tatanagar, Burnpur and Durgapur are rich in P₂O₅ content and hence suitable for nitrophosphate production. Basic slags of Bhilai, Rourkela and Bhadrabati not rich in P₂O₅ may be conveniently utilized for neutralizing acid soils.

The experimental results (Table 2) shows that with increasing urea nitrate content, the percentage of water soluble phosphate increases and at the stage of 1 : 2 ratio nearly 90% water soluble P₂O₅ is obtained. On further increasing the amount of urea nitrate the percentage of water soluble P₂O₅ only slightly increases and with 1 : 3 ratio the figure of water soluble phosphate reaches approximately 98%. It appears that basic slag reacts with urea nitrate in two stages according to the following equations—

The first stage which is a solid-solid reaction occurs on grinding the powders together at room temperature and in the second stage mono calcium phosphate is formed in the presence of excess urea nitrate. The second step is a solid-liquid reaction in which the nitric acid formed by the dissociation of urea nitrate reacts with dicalcium phosphate produced in the first step. This is supported by the fact that at the later stage of grinding, the powders form a paste. Further the work of Kutty and Murthy³ on solid phase reaction between calcium phosphate and urea nitrate confirms this type of reaction.

Phosphoric acid is a tribasic acid, strong for its first dissociation and weak for the second and third dissociation steps

According to Lowry-Bronsted acid—base concept HPO₄²⁻ and PO₄³⁻ are strong conjugate bases of weak acids in the successive stages of dissociation. Therefore calcium phosphate on treatment with aqueous nitric acid may give a mixture of CaHPO₄ and Ca(H₂PO₄)₂. But the action of urea nitrate on basic slag follows a different path and instead of di- and mono only water soluble monophosphate is obtained. The recent work on solid phase reaction between calcium phosphate and urea nitrate of Kutty and Murthy³ also confirms this type of reaction.

Some agricultural experts maintain that the water soluble P_2O_5 has definite superiority over the citrate soluble in alkaline soils and for short season crops, whereas in acidic soils citrate soluble P_2O_5 is as good as water soluble phosphate⁵. The production of nitrophosphatic fertilizer therefore will have this advantage. Moreover basic slag contains in addition to phosphorus and calcium, silicon, magnesium, manganese and some rare elements. Its silica content is effective in reducing the crop's demand for phosphorus and magnesium and manganese help in correcting soil deficiencies of these elements. Thus a mixed fertilizer made out of basic slag, due to the presence of secondary and rarer essential

elements will be the best shotgun for nutrient crop deficiencies of doubtful origin also.

References

1. N. H. FURMAN, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", Vol. 1. D. Van Nostrand Co. Inc., Princeton, New Jersey, 1962.
2. T. R. N. KUTTY and A. R. V. MURTHY, *Indian J. Tech.*, 1972, 10, 305.
3. T. R. N. KUTTY and A. R. V. MURTHY, *Indian J. Tech.*, 1972, 10, 408.
4. NYDEGGER, *Chem. Abs.*, 1921, 15, 2327.
5. T. R. VISWANATHAN, *Indian Chem. Engg.*, 1966, 8, 116.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co. London, 2nd Ed., 1958, p. 380.